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Missing links: Understanding blindness to safety risks

ESReDA Project Group on Risk Management and Knowledge

Outcomes from the interactive session of the ESReDA Athens seminar

This executive summary is an output from the interactive session organised by the ESReDA project group on Risk, Knowledge and Management at the ESReDA seminar held in Athens in November 2024. The seminar included a poster session with four posters, each with a claim concerning organisational blindness to safety risks. As part of the seminar, the audience was divided into four groups, and each group was asked to spend 20 minutes with a poster, then move on to the next one. At the poster, the audience was given a short presentation of the claim on the poster, and the background to it, and asked about their thoughts concerning the claim.

The objective of this summary is to thank the audience for their participation, and to give all participants a reminder of what the posters claimed, feedback on what was discussed in the interactive sessions, and information on what conclusions were then made. This executive summary does not claim to be the truth, but instead we hope it rouses thoughts and ideas on potential ways to reduce organisational blindness, better identify safety problems and ensure that the decisions required to reduce risks are not buried by the myriad of other pressures that affect every organisation.

The posters addressed different facets of organisational (and organised) blindness: (1) how complexity contributes to the blindness of organisations, (2) how you can be wilfully blind, (3) how to detect that you may be blind to issues, and (4) how you can tackle blindness with smarter communication. The discussions helped identify concepts and practices that can help reinforce the link that should exist between knowledge of threats to safety and the allocation of organisational resources to prevent accidents.

The first poster was about the dissemination of responsibility in complex systems in which people belonging to multiple organisations have to collaborate and coordinate to make decisions about safety management. In such systems, awareness concerning risks tends to be distributed, and accountability for safety is spread across several people and therefore weakened. We see this across multiple accidents including the Key Bridge accident (Baltimore, 2024), the Deepwater Horizon catastrophe, and the Grenfell Tower fire. These complex organisational structures are becoming increasingly common for multi-stakeholder systems and infrastructures, so we need to be aware of the associated challenges.

Several points were raised by the audience of the Athens seminar: First of all, this may often be seen in particular in systems which involve public and private partnership, and in which multiple stakeholders need to participate in the system governance. A “pass-the-buck” phenomenon is often seen when investigating accidents in such systems. Second, a strong regulatory framework can help avoid certain problems which appear with these complex organisational structures, but the strength of the regulatory system is very variable depending on the industry sector concerned. It is necessary to find effective collaboration and decision-making mechanisms despite the presence of silos, and despite diverging

interests from stakeholders. Finally, the participants pointed out that monolithic systems are not immune to these challenges because obstacles to information sharing and to clear accountability are also present inside systems run by a single organisation.

The second poster claimed that needed upgrades to engineering are sometimes stopped by wilful blindness. The participants agreed on that, noting a lack of strategies to deal with it. Wilful blindness was, however, expected to be more likely in some settings than others. The optimism of small business owners can be seen as an exercise in wilful blindness. Several participants pointed out that, beyond the usual adage *'if it ain't broke, don't fix it'*, the IT sector tightly embraces a culture of *'if it works, don't touch it'* and *'it's good enough'*. Hence, even if the client is mindful of risks, an overly pragmatic software development team might not be.

Our participants also noted that wilful blindness seems to be at work in discussions of reasonable practicability. These included: how experts are selected, how good practice is determined, how standard-setting bodies are governed, and how risks themselves are (subsequently) framed.

Foresight, one participant noted, gets worse gradually and is not easily restored. The concept of ethical fading implies a similar incrementalism. A participant noted that this dynamic has a social inertia. In practice, a group that migrates in increments to a new deviant norm is very reluctant to reverse its steps. A *'don't ask, don't tell'* culture is hard to undo once embedded. Stakeholder engagement, we would expect, should help to reduce wilful blindness, making it less likely or more easily countered. Likewise, if the relationships between the employer and the workforce are poor, as one of our participants noted, it can be hard for a manager to distinguish between valid concerns and the flexing of an agenda.

One of the participants spoke of his disappointment to find, on returning to his country after twenty years away, that some problems were unchanged. It was noted that, when one level of government is challenged, they are adept at blaming the level above. Wilful blindness can create its own *metarisk* of fueling mistrust in institutions and wider political processes.

The third poster was about early warning signs. We propose that detecting and acting on EWS are very important to get both knowledge management and risk management to a higher level of efficiency and effectiveness. Starting from the notion that an EWS is early, and warns of escalation, we build on past experience that if the EWS is not acted on, the disturbance-scenario will escalate and have a bigger impact leading up to a major accident. Therefore, the solution is to stop this escalation as soon as possible by detecting EWS and acting upon them with knowledge-based and evidence-based risk management. The main approach is to identify the components of the normal/abnormal flow which starts with an observation of reality and which - after e.g. data analysis, interpretation, information, knowledge, and decision making - should end with an action on that reality.

To progress to a solution it is very important to learn the boundaries of the safe region of operation, and that transgressing the boundaries is in fact an early warning sign that should prompt action. For example, the Key Bridge accident included several early warning signs - elements that were known concerning both

the status of the bridge and the situation on the vessel - examples which were used to kick off discussion with the interactive session participants.

The insights gained in from this interaction included that promoting diversity in teams (including shop-floor workers) is essential to support the interpretation of signals; that information overload can hide the critical information; that fostering a culture of feedback and learning is critical; that if the data is partial, incomplete, or influenced by biases, the conclusions drawn from it may be misleading, hindering the ability to detect warning signs.

The fourth poster was about communication: are accidents due to bad communication of the risk that is understood by the safety professional but not by the decision-maker who remains blind to it? How should the available knowledge be communicated so that it leads to the decision-maker both understanding the issues and acting upon them? Complex matters may lead to decision-makers focusing on only their own field of expertise and omitting the rest, or the decision-maker may already have decided and is not motivated to change.

According to the seminar discussions with the audience, smart communication is about defining what is the content, objective, and best method and timing of the communication, what evidence should be used, and identifying who should communicate to whom: to drive change, safety professionals should tailor the message to match the perception and judgement capabilities of the audience. At the same time, both the person sharing the information and the person receiving it need to understand that it takes effort to shift beliefs and gain understanding.

In conclusion, as key takeaways from the interactive session of the seminar, we now understand that we can treat corporations as entities, and individuals as entities, but we cannot treat a team or the system as an entity. When discussing blindness, we pick on individuals even though it is a team function, and could even be a corporate function. When everyone is responsible, no one is responsible. How organisations are organised internally for accountability, is important. Here, the framework to regulate how stakeholders engage and collaborate is of importance to help organisations 'do governance' and gain foresight.

Blindness can involve bad behaviour but usually the behaviour is within the normal range, but with a bad consequence. Perhaps this is a subject which like others is a matter of fitting the task to the person. Do we need to design our processes to more closely fit how people are, how they work together? Still, people are really reluctant to talk about blindness. Why: fear; denial? This has made the problem more or less undiscussable. We need to recognise that there are some rule sets that are lacking in the workplace. And sometimes a decision has to be made to slow down, think, and make more deliberate choices.

In the scope of blindness, early warning signs are an important element. Signals need to be identified and managed, not suppressed. Here, early warning signs are identifiable only if networks function: for example, by trouble-free collaboration between stakeholders, which would avoid signals being lost. We need something where early warning signs are talked about and acted upon. This does not happen

sometimes, maybe because the decision-making process is unwieldy. Here, a more agile process might be the answer, to avoid shortcuts and the blindness that comes with it.

There are ways to communicate that actually create blindness. Your message is also competing with other messages, and we probably do not think about communication as much as we should. You can always blame 'poor' communication after the fact, and you would be right, but that is not helpful. You need to think more concretely about the way you are communicating: you need to think strategically to get the best possible chance to gain results that make the difference in safety.

The poster sessions, and reflections since, make it clear that blindness is an issue to which we lack answers. However, blindness is usually discussed only in hindsight, and surrounded by negative emotions and recrimination. In the workplace, blindness is feared for its punishing consequences. To make progress, the subject first needs to be brought to light and made discussable.

A full paper with more detailed results and conclusions is planned to be released during 2025.